

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUKIIBI****FIRST NAME: ASHY****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%.

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D.

1. How does research-based writing differ from the other types of persuasive writing?
 - A) It relies solely on the writer's opinions and beliefs.
 - B) It rests on the shared facts that readers accept as truth independent of personal feelings and beliefs.¹**
 - C) Evidence is not required to support these claims.
 - D) It invites readers to accept claims without critical thinking.
2. Which of the following is an example of an unhelpful plan for drafting a research paper?
 - A) Creating a detailed outline based on your storyboard.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 6.

- B) Writing an introduction that sketches your main argument.
- C) **Assembling a draft that is a patchwork of quotations and summaries from sources.²**
- D) Using key terms to create subheads for each section.
3. What was one of the main goals of your final introduction?
- A) To list all your sources.
- B) To provide a detailed methodology.
- C) **To establish a context of prior research.³**
- D) To include all your data.
4. Which action could still result in plagiarism, even if you cite the source accurately?
- A) Transcribing words exactly as they are in the original.
- B) Using only reliable, relevant sources.
- C) Accurately reporting sources in your bibliography.
- D) **Using the exact words of the source without identifying them as a quotation.⁴**
5. How should numbers one to nine be generally written in the text?
- A) Always use digits for numbers one to nine.

² Ibid., 67.

³ Ibid., 106.

⁴ Ibid., 359.

- B) Spell numbers one to nine and use the digits thereafter.**⁵
- C) Always use figures for all numbers on the webpages.
- D) Use digits for numbers one–nine only in legal documents.
6. In which order should descriptive adjectives appear before a noun?
- A) Size, age or shape, colour, origin or nationality, material.**⁶
- B) Age or shape, size, colour, material, origin or nationality.
- C) Colour, size, age or shape, origin or nationality, material.
- D) Material, origin or nationality, colour, age or shape, size.
7. What is the appropriate abbreviation for the European Commission's main administrative division?
- A) D.G.
- B) DG**⁷
- C) d.g.
- D) D-G
8. How should references to the Official Journal of the European Union be formatted in the footnotes?
- A) OJ L 118 of 4 May 1973, p. 1.

⁵ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (The European Union, 2016), 35.

⁶ Ibid., 50.

⁷ Ibid., 91.

- B) Official Journal L 118 of 4 May 1973.
- C) OJ No. L 118 of 4 May 1973, p. 1.
- D) OJ L 118 of 4 May 1973.⁸**
9. What is the correct format for naming a Response Paper (RP) file?
- A) First Name_Last Name_Program Code_Course Code_Paper Code.
- B) FirstName-LastName-ProgramCode-CourseCode-PaperCode.
- C) First Name _ Last Name _ Program Code _ Course Code _ Paper Code.⁹**
- D) First.Name. Last.Name. Program.Code. Course.Code. Paper.Code.
10. What should every response paper contain to support these main points?
- A) At least five well-placed in-text citations from any source.
- B) At least ten well-placed in-text citations from the prescribed study material for the period.¹⁰**
- C) At least ten well-placed in-text citations from Internet sources.
- D) At least five well-placed in-text citations from any book.
11. How should long quotations be formatted in a paper?
- A) Enclosed in quotation marks and followed by the author's name and page number.

⁸ Ibid., 93.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *How to Write a Response Paper (RP)* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 2.

¹⁰ Ibid., 4.

- B) Indented without quotation marks and followed by the author's name and page number.¹¹**
- C) Enclosed in quotation marks and not followed by the author's name and page number.
- D) Indented without quotation marks and not followed by the author's name and page number.

12. what should be included when reporting the internal consistency of scales and subscales from measures used in dissertation research?

- A) Provide a summary of key findings.
- B) Include references for any uncommon statistical analyses.
- C) Report inter-rater reliability for all measures.
- D) Report coefficient alpha reliabilities.¹²**

¹¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fifth Edition* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

¹² James P Sampson Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 54.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.